

Appendix

Configurable AI Coding Assistants: Designing For Developers Who Like to Be in Control

February, 2026

Appendix A.1

Survey script

This survey is about configurations, or controls/settings, that you can set up in your coding AI assistant. They apply across all interactions, not just individual prompts. For example, adding "please use spaces" to a single prompt is not a configuration but having a toggle that makes the assistant always use spaces is. We're interested in which configurations you use today, which ones you'd like to see, and how much control you want over your assistant's behavior and output.

This survey takes about 15 minutes to complete. Thank you for taking the time to share your thoughts with us!

Survey Terms and Conditions *

What is your country or region?*

[Choice of countries]

What is your employment status?*

[Single-choice question]

- Fully employed by a company / organization
- Partially employed by a company / organization
- Self-employed (earning income directly from your own business, trade, or profession)
- Freelancer (pursuing a profession without a long-term commitment to any one employer)
- Working Student
- Student [END survey]
- Retired [END survey]
- Other, please specify: [END survey]

How many years of professional coding experience do you have?*

[Single-choice question]

- Less than 2 [END survey]
- 3-5
- 6-10
- 11-16

- 16+ years
- I don't have any work experience [END survey]

Which of the following best describes your job role(s) regardless of your position level?*

[Multiple-choice question]

- Team Lead (!)
- DevOps Engineer, Infrastructure Developer, etc. (!)
- Developer Advocate
- DBA (!)
- Instructor, Teacher, Tutor, etc.
- Product or Project Manager (!)
- Developer, Programmer, or Software Engineer (!)
- Data Analyst, Data Engineer, or Data Scientist (!)
- CIO, CEO, or CTO
- Systems Analyst (!)
- Architect (!)
- UX/UI Designer (!)
- Technical Support
- Tester or QA Engineer (!)
- Technical Writer
- Other, please specify:

[If no (!) position has been checked – END survey]

How long have you been using coding AI assistants in your work?*

[Single-choice question]

- I normally don't use GenAI for coding [END survey]
- less than 6 months [END survey]
- 7-11 months [END survey]
- 1-2 years
- More than 2 years

How frequently do you normally use coding AI assistants in your work?*

[Single-choice question]

- Every day
- Several times a week
- Once a week
- 2-3 times a month or less frequently [END survey]

Which AI assistants do you use for coding tasks?*

[Multiple-choice question]

- ChatGpt
- GitHub Copilot
- Cursor

- JetBrains AI Assistant
- DeepSeek
- Gemini
- Anthropic Claude
- JetBrains Junie
- Meta Code Llama
- Tabnine
- Ghostwriter
- CodiumAI
- Visual Studio IntelliCode
- Other, please specify:

Do you use any coding AI assistants inside your IDE (for example, as a plugin)?*

[Single-choice question]

- Yes
- No

What is your company's overall stance on the use of coding AI assistants at work? *

[Single-choice question]

- Coding AI assistants are strictly forbidden
- It's allowed, but only with strict restrictions (e.g., no sensitive data, tool approvals)
- It's generally allowed with minimal restrictions
- It's actively encouraged and promoted by leadership
- I'm not sure / It hasn't been clearly communicated
- I don't work in a company

Which of the following tasks do you primarily use your coding AI assistant for?*

[Multiple-choice question]

- Search for answers
- Generating content or synthetic data
- Learning new concepts or technologies
- Documenting code (e.g. docstring)
- Creating or maintaining documentation (e.g. README)
- Learning about a codebase
- Debugging or fixing code
- Code refactoring or optimization
- Committing and reviewing code
- Testing code
- Data analysis
- DevOps or automation tasks
- Brainstorming
- Other, please specify:

Characteristics of the Code Suggestion:

We will now show you the list of configurations for AI code suggestions. These configurations are about structure, style and technologies used in the code the assistant suggests: from formatting and language choice to the libraries it uses and how much detail it includes.

[Configurations list]

- Preferred code style and formatting
e.g., tabs or spaces, naming conventions
- Restricted APIs, libraries, and files
- Preferred programming language(s), versions, and environment constraints
e.g., use React with TypeScript and not plain JS, generate code compatible with Python 3.8
- Framework or architecture conventions
e.g., functional or. OOP, preferred design patterns
- Preferred testing style
e.g., include unit tests by default, use Jest for testing
- Preferred documentation style
e.g., generate docstrings, inline comments, or no comments unless asked
- Optimization priorities
e.g., prioritize readability or performance or memory

For each setting, please tell us whether it exists as a system configuration in your current AI tools for software development.*

[Single-choice question]

- It exists
- It doesn't exist

For each configuration, please tell us how useful it is or would be for your workflow.*

[Single-choice question]

- Not useful
- Moderately useful
- Very useful

Is there anything else you'd like to control about how the assistant writes code for you?

[Open text box]

Characteristics of the System and Policies:

We will now show you the list of higher level assistant configurations. These configurations let you define preferences related to memory, data handling, execution boundaries, and compliance with policies.

[Configurations list]

- Model selection
- Chat memory depth
- Memory management and cleanup e.g., delete memorized chats
- On-premise vs. off-premise execution
- Data retention and privacy preferences e.g., opt-out of logging conversations for training
- Suggestion validation e.g., Legal license, static analysis, organization style guideline, etc.

- Organizational governance integration e.g., connect to internal policy engines or shared style guides and linters
- User role-based access or permissions e.g., interns' assistants aren't allowed to change codebase and access specific files
- Network or data access controls e.g., disallow web search, access to internal databases, or external APIs

For each setting, please tell us whether it exists as a system configuration in your current AI tools for software development.*

[Single-choice question]

- It exists
- It doesn't exist

For each configuration, please tell us how useful it is or would be for your workflow.*

[Single-choice question]

- Not useful
- Moderately useful
- Very useful

Is there anything else you'd like to control about how the assistant writes code for you?

[Open text box]

Characteristics of Human-Assistant Interaction

We will now show you the list of coding AI assistant interaction configurations. These configurations focus on how the assistant communicates with you: how it responds, when it responds, and how it looks.

[Configurations list]

- Preferred response length
- Custom shortcuts
- Response timing and triggering behavior e.g. only when prompted, frequent autocompletions, snoozed autocompletions
- Appearance of code completions e.g., position in editor (inline, pop-up), opacity or background shading
- Showing confidence or quality scores for suggestions
- Minimum confidence threshold to show completions
- Preferred form of address e.g., by first name, nickname, honorifics, or anonymous ("Hey dev!")
- Assign a persona to the assistant e.g. work buddy, senior expert, review bot, code generation tool
- Preferred communication style e.g., concise or detailed, formal or casual, suggestive or directive

For each setting, please tell us whether it exists as a system configuration in your current AI tools for software development.*

[Single-choice question]

- It exists
- It doesn't exist

For each configuration, please tell us how useful it is or would be for your workflow.*

[Single-choice question]

- Not useful

- Moderately useful
- Very useful

Is there anything else you'd like to control about how the assistant writes code for you?

[Open text box]

Characteristics of the Developer and their work context

We will now show you the list of user personalization configurations. These configurations focus on the user, their personality, abilities, and work context, so the assistant can adapt to the user's individual needs and professional context.

[Configurations list]

- Gender identity or pronoun preferences
- Custom job title or role specification to adjust guidance and expectations e.g., "Senior Frontend Engineer," "Tech Lead," "QA Intern"
- Accessibility settings e.g., screen reader compatibility, text size, contrast options
- Familiar with AI assistant e.g. novice, experienced user
- Business context integration e.g., connect to project management tools like YouTrack, Jira, or GitHub Issues for task-aware assistance
- Personal goals or development focus e.g., "I'm trying to learn React," or "I want to improve my test coverage habits"
- Workstyle profiling e.g., via lightweight personality test or user-selected archetype (e.g., "strategist," "hacker," "careful editor")
- Preferred learning style e.g., hands-on guidance or high-level suggestions, step-by-step explanations or summary results

For each setting, please tell us whether it exists as a system configuration in your current AI tools for software development.*

[Single-choice question]

- It exists
- It doesn't exist

For each configuration, please tell us how useful it is or would be for your workflow.*

[Single-choice question]

- Not useful
- Moderately useful
- Very useful

Is there anything else you'd like to control about how the assistant writes code for you?

[Open text box]

Thank you for your participation

Is there anything else you would like to control and configure in your coding AI assistant? Why is it important to you?

[Open text box]

Do you typically adjust your coding AI assistant’s configurations, or stick with the defaults?*

[Single-choice question]

- I usually leave all configurations at their default
- I’ve made a few small changes
- I actively configure the assistant to fit my needs
- I wasn’t aware configurations could be changed

Would you like to participate in the further interviews regarding coding AI assistants configurations? If yes, please leave your email and name below.

[Open text box]

Appendix A.1

Survey results

Per-configuration usefulness and availability over 56 survey participants and 33 configurations. Positive usefulness counts **Moderately** and **Very useful** as positive. Mean usefulness uses ordinal coding (**Not**=0, **Moderately**=1, **Very**=2). Existence is the percentage of participants who report knowing about the configuration existing in their current AI tools. We underline the highest values in each of four groups.

Configuration	Positive usefulness (%)	Mean usefulness (0-2)	Existence (%)
Preferred code style and formatting	82.1%	1.36	44.6%
Restricted APIs, libraries, and files	83.9%	1.16	33.9%
Preferred programming languages, versions, and environment constraints	91.1%	1.48	48.2%
Framework or architecture conventions	85.7%	1.41	51.8%
Preferred testing style	87.5%	1.32	42.9%
Preferred documentation style	83.9%	1.21	44.6%
Optimization priorities	82.1%	1.21	32.1%
Model selection	94.6%	1.80	91.1%
Chat memory depth	78.6%	1.09	39.3%
Memory management and cleanup	66.1%	0.91	35.7%
On-premises vs. off-premises execution	71.4%	1.02	17.9%
Data retention and privacy preferences	87.5%	1.46	55.4%
Suggestion validation	85.7%	1.30	30.4%
Organizational governance integration	85.7%	1.30	19.6%
User role-based access or permissions	66.1%	0.98	19.6%
Network or data access controls	68.9%	1.02	35.7%
Preferred response length	91.1%	1.55	28.6%
Custom shortcuts	58.9%	0.80	51.8%
Response timing and triggering behavior	78.6%	1.18	32.1%
Appearance of code completions	64.3%	0.88	60.7%
Showing confidence or quality scores for suggestions	87.5%	1.39	19.6%
Minimum confidence threshold to show completions	87.5%	1.41	19.6%
Preferred form of address	48.2%	0.68	23.2%
Assign a persona to the assistant	51.8%	0.79	19.6%
Preferred communication style	82.1%	1.23	32.1%
Gender identity or pronoun preferences	21.4%	0.32	12.5%
Custom job title or role specification to adjust guidance and expectations	35.7%	0.54	16.1%
Accessibility settings	62.5%	0.89	46.4%
Familiarity with AI tools for software development	46.4%	0.70	17.9%
Business context integration	76.8%	1.18	37.5%
Personal goals or development focus	62.5%	0.98	23.2%
Workstyle profiling	53.6%	0.80	16.1%
Preferred learning style	78.6%	1.13	35.7%

Appendix B

Design session and Interview Script

Hello, our names are [NAMES], I'm a researcher at [AFFILIATION].

First of all, thank you once again for agreeing to participate, we truly appreciate your time and insights. To give you a bit of context, the goal of this study is to better understand developers' needs and expectations when it comes to customizing AI coding tools. We're especially interested in which customization configurations you use most often, why they matter to you, and whether there are any configurations you wish you had but currently don't.

This session will be approximately 1 hour long and is divided into two parts:

1. A designing session in Miro board where we explore what kinds of configurations you need and how they could work.
2. An interview, where we discuss the results of the session and talk about what influences your customization choices.

Just to clarify, the purpose of this study is to learn from your experiences and needs. We're not evaluating your skills in any way and there are no right or wrong answers.

Before we begin, let's check that you can open and edit Miro board that we'll use for the session. I would also like to record this session. The recordings will remain confidential. We will anonymize the data and create summaries for research purposes only. Once the study is complete, all recordings will be deleted, and no personal information will be shared. Is that okay with you? Great, I'll start the recording now. Once it begins, I'll ask for your confirmation to record this session.

OK, then, let's proceed. Before we start the design session, we would like to learn a little bit about your background.

In the survey, you've said you've been using coding AI tools for [TIME] and that you tried [TOOLS]. Is that correct? Which ones are you still using?

Now, when you use AI coding tools, do you customize them in any way, or are you happy with all the default configurations?

Can you describe a situation where lack of customization influenced your experience with a coding AI tool?

Now, let's move on to the design session. Here is the link to the Miro board where you will be working for the next 20 minutes.

Let's start with the warm-up task to get you comfortable with the system and the idea of the design session. You can see an empty setting screen for PyCharm. And on the right side, you can see little panels with all the possible configurations: Python, Appearance, Version Control, Editor, and Languages. If you're not familiar with these configurations, next to them if you follow the line, you'll see their descriptions and lists specific controls they have. Your task now is just to prioritize these configurations from the most useful or important or whatever other metric you want to use on the top, to the least on the bottom. For that, just drag each little panel to the currently empty configurations screen and order them on it. While you're doing it, try to think aloud: share your thoughts, reactions, or any challenges that come to mind while you're doing the task. You can start now, please let me know if there is anything you don't understand or need help with.

[5-10 MINUTES]

Now, let's move on to the design session itself. You can find the task a bit below on the same Miro board.

You can see two screens in the middle. First one on the left is a settings window that you can find and open inside of your IDE. It normally requires a few clicks to open it but it has all the space you want in the world. The other on the right is the AI assistant's chat window where we normally place some quick access settings that don't require a lot of space. Your task now is to choose which settings, or configurations, you want to have in your ideal coding AI assistant, and how you would like to control them. You can resize these screens to your liking, and make them bigger if you need more space.

On the right side of the screens, you can find a list of configurations we have already written out for you. If you want to use one of these options you just take a rectangle with it and drag it to one of two screens, the way you did in the trial task. You don't have to use all these configurations, only the ones you like. And if you would like to add a setting not from this list, you can also do it by copying the empty rectangle and writing a name for the new setting in it.

We would also like you to choose how you want to adjust your configurations. On the left side of the screens, you can see different control widgets: a toggle, a slider, a text box, a multiple choice checklist, and a one-choice radio button. For each setting you pick and place on one of the two screens, next to it place a widget, showing how you want to control it. For that, use copy-paste. If you think of another control which we don't have here, please say it and we'll figure out how to represent it.

For example, I want to use this setting and have it in a quick access window. So, I drag the name of the setting to the window. And let's say I want to control it with a radiobutton, do I copy the widget from the left side, and put the widget right next to it. Do you understand the idea and what you need to do?

Please, don't forget to think aloud while you're doing the task. Share your thoughts, reactions, or any challenges that come to mind while doing the task. So that we could better understand your thought process and perspective.

[15-20 MINUTES]

Can you walk us through what you created? Let's go through each setting you picked.

- When in your workflow will this setting affect your work the most and how? [check what they said in the survey about it existing and being useful, confirm]
- Was there a specific situation or problem that prompted you to want to have control over this?
- Why this type of widget? Why quick access window? [possibly, depending on their choice]

What influences your need for customization the most? For example, trust in the tool, company policy, personal efficiency, or something else?

Do you have any final thoughts on what an ideal customizable AI coding assistant should look like?

Thank you so much for sharing your thoughts with us today. Before we wrap up, is there anything else you'd like to add that we haven't covered yet?